

The shadow of failed organ incorporation in transplantation. A literary analogy

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Abstract (203 words)

Background: The psychological integration of a transplanted organ (heart, kidney)—meaning it becomes part of the recipient's body—is crucial for long-term success. The literature suggests this is generally the case for most organ recipients. The French philosopher Nancy described his new heart as an “intruder”—something foreign that entered his body and altered his sense of self. He regarded the allograft as a shadow that betrayed him. **Material and Methods:** Analysis of two novels, with detailed attention to the shadow motif. The hypothesis of this essay is to draw analogies between two novels (“Peter Schlemihl's Remarkable Story” by Adelbert von Chamisso and Hans Christian Andersen's “Shadow”) and Nancy's personal experience. **Results:** In both stories, the shadow is not merely a physical phenomenon; it signifies something fundamental about the self. A transplanted organ that is not fully incorporated may be viewed as a shadow that becomes independent and even hostile to its host. **Conclusion:** Therefore, achieving complete psychological integration of the transplant into the body image is essential, and these two novels serve as a reminder of the negative outcomes if this is not accomplished. Novels could illustrate the significant consequences of the failed integration of transplanted organs into the body.

Introduction

Successful incorporation of a foreign allograft into the body schema, meaning that the organ recipient no longer considers the transplant as foreign but rather as an integral part of their own body, is important for the long-term function of the organ as well as the overall survival of the recipient (1-3). Clinical surveys indicate that this is the case in the majority of patients (>90%). A notable exception is the personal experience of the French philosopher Jean-Luc Nancy (1940-2021), who received a heart transplant in 1981 because of irreversible heart failure and struggled to accept and incorporate this allograft. He described his feelings and experiences in the small book “The Intruder” from 2020 (4, published in French in 2024 and in English in 2024). In this contribution, Nancy deconstructed the concept of a clearly defined personal identity by blurring self and otherness in corporeality, with the allograft floating over the person like a shadow.

This manuscript seeks to draw parallels between Nancy's experiences and the motif of the shadow (5) in the fairy tale of the same name by Hans Christian Andersen (1805-1875), and in the novel Peter Schlemihl (6) by Adelbert von Chamisso, in which shadows become separated from their owners and eventually oppose and work against them. A failed integration of a transplanted allograft may be seen as a shadow that is continuously refused yet shackled to the recipient, ultimately annihilating the recipient through complications of chronic rejection.

Hans Christian Andersen The shadow (original title: Skyggen) from 1847 (5)

In his fairy tale “The Shadow,” the famous Danish author Hans Christian Andersen tells the story of a learned man who moves from cold to hot countries. There, he jokingly orders his shadow to go into the mysterious house opposite and see who lives there.

However, the shadow uses its newfound freedom to “earn” money through clever blackmail and eventually becomes human. When the shadow visits its master after several years, it recounts its experiences. On a second visit, the scholar accepts the shadow's offer to travel with him. Upon their arrival, the shadow marries the king's daughter. On the day of the wedding, the shadow offers his former master the opportunity to earn a living as a servant in his castle. The shadow uses the scholar's subsequent threat to reveal the shadow's past to the king's daughter, thereby having him imprisoned and ultimately murdered. It is obvious that the two main characters in the fairy tale, the shadow and the learned man, have completely different personalities. Right at the beginning of the text, the author characterises the learned man as young and clever. This can be seen, among other things, in the fact that he writes books himself, albeit not very successfully. After moving to the hot countries, the learned man suffers from the intense heat. These unusually high temperatures affect the man so much that he becomes “very thin” (line 10). He lives in a narrow street with tall buildings (5). The silence in the mysterious house opposite intrigues the scholar, but he is reluctant to investigate who lives there. The music he hears from inside the room seems “incomparably beautiful” to him (5). However, Andersen relativises this by admitting that the man finds everything except the sun “incomparably beautiful” (5). When he sends his shadow to the balcony opposite one evening as a joke, he only notices the next day that it has disappeared without a trace.

A similar disturbing confrontation with a shadow is described in Adelbert von Chamisso (1781–1838), Peter Schlemihl (OT: Peter Schlemihls wundersame Geschichte) from 1814 (6).

Peter Schlemihl is an insecure young man when he arrives at the very wealthy Mr John's house with a letter of recommendation. Mr John is hosting a garden party, so Schlemihl's arrival is somewhat inconvenient. However, he is not sent away. Instead, as a kind of onlooker, he meets a strange man dressed in grey who entertains the guests by conjuring up the most incredible things from his coat: a telescope, a carpet, a marquee, and finally even three saddled horses. No one at the party seems to find anything strange about this, but Peter Schlemihl finds the whole thing increasingly eerie. When he leaves the party, the grey-clad man follows him and offers him a deal: he wants Peter Schlemihl's shadow and offers him a bag of luck in return, with which he can fulfil any wish from now on.

Peter Schlemihl accepts and is now a rich man. But he quickly realises what he has got himself into. Everywhere he goes, people are frightened when they notice his lack of a shadow; children mock him, and soon he no longer dares to go out in public. He tries to find the grey man again to undo the ill-fated exchange. But the grey man only tells him he will be back in exactly one year (6).

Peter Schlemihl settles in a seaside resort where no one knows him personally, yet he is regarded as important because of his wealth. Only his faithful servant Bendel knows of his lack of a shadow and does his best to hide it from the public. Schlemihl falls in love with the forester's daughter, Mina, and announces to her father that he will soon ask for her hand in marriage. But first, one important matter must be settled. The year is almost over, and Peter Schlemihl hopes to get his shadow back. Indeed, the Grey

Man appears and offers to return it. However, he demands a signature in blood, by which Peter Schlemihl bequeaths his soul to him. Peter refuses and loses his Mina.

From then on, Schlemihl tries to flee from the devil (for the Grey Man is none other than the devil), but he is caught up again and again (6). Only when the devil pulls a damned soul out of his pocket before his very eyes — the rich Mr John, whom Schlemihl once admired so much — does he free himself by throwing the bag of luck into the abyss. But Peter Schlemihl remains a lonely and restless man forever. With his now meagre funds, he buys a pair of old boots at a fair, which turn out to be seven-league boots. Effortlessly, but not quite humanly, he travels to the most remote parts of the world and devotes himself to exploring nature. The shadow in Peter Schlemihl may primarily represent human identity, because those without a shadow are no longer considered “real” human beings. By losing his shadow, Schlemihl loses part of his personality and his place in society, as well as social recognition and dignity, since without it he is viewed with suspicion, excluded, and ridiculed. The shadow thus symbolises what makes a person acceptable in society. Finally, the shadow reflects moral conscience and inner wholeness.

What are the common features of the shadows in both works?

In both stories, the shadow likely represents human identity, or at least part of it. Those who lose their shadow (Schlemihl) or are dominated by it (as in Andersen's story) lose their social recognition and their sense of self. The shadows have independent lives. They are not merely simple reflections but develop a life of their own. Schlemihl's shadow is completely missing, which may suggest social exclusion. In Andersen's story, the shadow even becomes more powerful than its owner. In both texts, an uneven power relationship develops between the original owner and the shadow. Schlemihl becomes dependent and isolated due to the absence of his shadow, whereas in Andersen's story, the man is even forced to submit to his own shadow.

The Israeli-British philosopher Havid Carel [born 1971], who herself suffers from a Chronic, progressive lung disease, Carel's account of which proposes that Anderson's fairy tale may reflect the complex situation of an individual after organ transplantation. Carel wrote: “As a result of this metaphysical adventure, the intruder/shadow becomes master: the grafted organ has been incorporated, but even medical success cannot eradicate the intrusion. Like the shadow, incorporation is not possible. The transplanted heart can substitute the explanted heart; it cannot incorporate it, and thus “[the intruder's] coming will not cease”. The intruder/shadow becomes the man himself” (7, p. 166). Carel suggests that a transplanted organ, if not psychologically incorporated, imposes dramatic changes on the recipient's psyche and body, similar to the shadow's effect on the scholar. Nancy's feelings towards his heart transplant remain alien, and his original identity is lost, as with Peter's shadow. Is Nancy's feeling towards his transplanted organ typical for recipients of allografts after transplantation? Probably not, and Nancy's feelings are rather extreme.

Conclusion

Nancy felt that the medical complications (including rejections) after transplantation altered his personality, and he sees the transplanted heart as a shadow betraying him,

similar to the shadows who acted against the original owners in A. T. von Chamisso's and H. C. Andersen's stories.

However, the medical situation, beyond Nancy's individual feelings, may be more complex, as I proposed almost 2025 years ago when analysing the T. Mann novel "The Transposed Heads", which describes a fictional head transplantation (8). Since the immune system functions through the affinity of a T cell receptor for a certain peptide, the presentation of peptides by the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) ultimately governs whether or not T cells are activated.¹⁵ Foreign peptides are perceived in the context of self, that is, the MHC. Consequently, the self may be defined in molecular terms by MHC alleles (9, 10). Since the MHC is defined by an inherited set of genes, the basis for this self would then be given a priori (9). Consequently, organ rejection after allograft transplantation may be the ultimate situation in which, during the immune process of allograft rejection, the self emerges (11). One could speculate that personality, as a biological concept, might only become apparent in the interaction of self MHC genes with the outside world of non-self foreign antigens. Ultimately, the transplant rejection process would define the self. A successful transplantation of any organ, with immunosuppressive therapy preventing allograft rejection, might therefore hinder the emergence of the self in the long term (8).

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Disclosure statement

There is nothing to disclose